

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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GRAMMATICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODAL WORDS IN ENGLISH.

Xuliya Argana

Doctoral student at Dicle university

Mustafayeva Maftuna Bahodirovna

assistant teacher of "TIIAME" National Research University Karshi Institute of
Irrigation and Agrotechnology

Annotation. This article talks about modal words and their important role in linguistics, which have been carefully studied and analyzed by world scientists and linguists of the English language. Since modals are the cause of much discussion and controversy in linguistics, this article analyzes the grammatical and semantic functions of modals.

Key words: modal word, etymology, semantics, development, grammar, linguistics, subjective, objective, introductory words.

ГРАММАТИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА МОДАЛЬНЫХ СЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ.

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о модальных словах и их важной роли в лингвистике, которые были тщательно изучены и проанализированы мировыми учеными и лингвистами английского языка. Поскольку модальные слова являются причиной широких дискуссий и споров в лингвистике, в данной статье анализируются грамматические и семантические функции модальных слов.

Ключевые слова: модальное слово, этимология, семантика, развитие, грамматика, лингвистика, субъективные, объективное, вводные слова.

In linguistics, in order to study and fully understand any language phenomenon, this phenomenon should be covered from both the lexical and grammatical aspects.

It is worth noting that since the grammatical structure of any language is formed over several periods and gradually changes continuously, any grammatical

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phenomenon today can be understood only by studying it from the perspective of the historical development of this phenomenon.

Based on the rules of Marxist linguistics, we will try to explain the grammatical features of modal words from the etymological, morphological and syntactic point of view.

1. The question of the origin of modal words in the modern English language is of primary importance, and that is why they are of great interest in linguistics.

Modal words and phrases such as “*maybe, perhaps, possibly, probably, apparently, evidently, obviously, manifestly, no doubt, surely, of course, certainly*” emerged from the depths of important parts of speech during a long development.

Language never freezes in one place, it constantly evolves along with the people who use it as a means of communication. Consequently, the migration and transition of words from one group to another and the formation of new word groups takes place at the bottom of the language. During the transition of words from one category to another, the accumulation of new qualitative elements occurs both grammatically and lexically. This word is either reinterpreted or its meaning weakened. At the same time, the word loses its old grammatical features and acquires new ones. Ultimately, as a result of the process, the lexical meaning changes completely and loses all grammatical features, and they are replaced by a completely new lexical content and some grammatical features that retain their new or partially old meanings. [1:115]

However, not every word can move to another part of speech, and not every word can develop new quality elements that would put it in the category of modal words. For this, the word should have potential possibilities that help this word move to the modal group of words. The only condition for removing any lexical unit from the original word group and transferring it to the modal word group is the true meaning of the word. In order for a word to have a modal meaning, its lexical meaning should not simply describe the facts of reality, but should have a meaning capable of evaluating these facts in terms of the level of reality. For example, verbs like *to suppose, to seem, to appear, to believe, to think* have necessary probability, like nouns like “*truth*” and adjectives like “*sure*”, “*certain*”.

Words of this type can serve as the basis for the formation of modal words or modal word combinations according to their potential characteristics. In addition, these words express abstract concepts, which helps the word to change to modal.

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However, nouns such as “*beauty*”, “*cleverness*”, “*satisfaction*” are considered abstract, but there is no information to add them to modal words. A word's ability to evaluate the phenomenon expressed in another word or sentence from the point of view of reality, the word's ability to be abstracted according to its meaning, and the wide field of application are the necessary conditions for dividing the word into a modal unit [2:265].

We can distinguish 3 formations in the group of modal words and phrases we are studying:

1. As a representative of the first group, we can take as an example one modal word “*maybe*” composed of two verbs: “*may*” + “*be*”. Following the same structure, the English words “*may fall*” and “*mayhap*” also exist, which are now obsolete. The Oxford dictionary points to the origin of the word “*maybe*” and states that this word is separated from the sentence “*It may be*” [3]. At this point, it is appropriate to recall the opinions of Russian linguists Shakhmatov and Potebnya about abbreviated sentences, which they consider to be “Introductory words”. “They (introductory words) come back to reduced sentences and real sentences” [4:185].

It should be noted that it is almost impossible to talk about the complete preservation of the meaning of the components of “*maybe*”. Because a certain loss of meaning undoubtedly occurred in the process of separating it from the verbal compound and projecting this word as a modal.

This can be evidenced by two cases:

1. The intonation design of “*maybe*” in modern English. Since the emphasis falls on the first component of “*Maybe*”, this leads to the weakening of the second part of the word.

2. The possibility of using the word “*maybe*” closely and appropriately with the verb “*to be*”. Maybe he is here and He maybe is here.

Group 2 modal forms include: *perhaps, no doubt, of course*.

They belong to the same group because they are based on a noun with an additional auxiliary element. “*Perhaps*” is formed from the plural noun “*hap*” and the prefix “*per*”. The Old English word “*hap*” means “*chance, luck*”. The prefix “*per*” as an etymological element means “*through, complete*”. This formation is not unique in Old English, but there are other words of exactly the same form with the same meaning, such as *percase, percance, peradventure*. All these words, except the word “*perhaps*”, are archaic and have fallen out of use. Since the word “*hap*” has

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also fallen out of use, the word “perhaps” has lost its connection with this noun, and its stem “hap” is no longer accepted as a noun.

If we turn to the analysis of the words “no doubt” and “of course”, it is very controversial and still not resolved whether these words are considered as a phrase or a word.

Both elements of the modal phrase “No doubt” are united into one semantic, indivisible whole. The semantics of this noun helped determine whether this phrase is modal. The formation of this modal phrase is based on the meaning of “doubt”, which forms its semantic core. Lexically, the accumulation of a new adjective began in close connection with the second element - the pronoun “no”.

Grammatically, the separation of the modal phrase “no doubt” from the noun “doubt” is expressed in the loss of morphological and syntactic features specific to the noun:

1. The noun “doubt” cannot be replaced by numbers in the modal phrase “no doubt”.
2. This noun cannot be combined with any definition.
3. Functionally, it cannot function as a member of the sentence.

The development stage of the modal “of course” is more complicated than the path of the modal combination “no doubt”. The formation process of the modal combination “no doubt” consists of narrowing the dictionary meaning of the noun “doubt”, keeping only one meaning “doubt” and removing its previous meanings such as *danger*, *fear*, as well as the noun caused it to lose its characteristic grammatical features and syntactic connections with other members of the sentence. When the group of modal words was separated, the prepositional phrase “of course” not only lost its previously characteristic grammatical connection with the members of the sentence, but also had to be completely revised in terms of content.

The Oxford dictionary gives 32 meanings of the word “course”, most of which are out of context. Section 19 of the dictionary gives the following meaning of this word: “*Habitually or ordinary manner of procedure, way, custom, practice*”.

From this meaning of the word “Course” the prepositional phrases “in course” and “of course” were formed. According to the dictionary definition, “in course” means “naturally, as expected”, while “of course” is used synonymously with “in course”. From the 16th century, “of course” began to be used in defining

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and descriptive tasks. Its modal meaning developed much later, towards the middle of the 19th century, and began to be used as an adverb “of course”:

It was at one time made a question whether giving the royal assent to a single bill did not of course put an end to the session. (Stephen, 1845)

The modern modal “*of course*” is a revised prepositional phrase “*of course*”, which was previously used in an adverbial function.

The third group of modal words is the most commonly used modal word in English. Examples of these are the following: possibly, probably, apparently, evidently, obviously, manifestly, surely, certainly. The structural structure of these words is clear and unambiguous and does not cause any confusion: *adjective + suffix + “ly”*. Among these words, “*possibly*” and “*probably*” are considered modal words, and the rest can be used not only in this task, but also in the adverbial task. Of course, this rarely happens.

There is no doubt that the lexical meaning of the adjective that forms the basis of the derived word is of great importance and cannot be ignored. In this case, the semantics of the words “*possible*” and “*probable*” with the help of the suffix “*ly*” means that the derivatives “*possibly*” and “*probably*” naturally retain the meanings of “*possibility*” and “*probability*”. The meanings of “*probability*” and “*possibility*” could become only modal words as abstract meanings capable of expressing the speaker's opinion about the level of reality of someone or an event. Adjectives such as “*apparent, evident, obvious, manifest*” are considered to be modal words with the suffix “*ly*” after them the process of separate separation continued along the stages of development of the abstraction of concrete elements and the abstract elements characteristic of qualities. We can see this process of abstraction, for example, in the modal word “*obviously*”. The original specific meaning of this adverb was directly related to the specific meaning of the adjective “*obviously*”. The English word “*obvious*” comes from the Latin adjective “*obvius*”, the components of which are the prefix “*ob*” meaning “*against*” and the noun “*via*” meaning “*way*” [5 :180].

To conclude, the subjective element is very important in the development of modal meaning in a word. The level of the subjective element contributes to the “*modalization*” of the word. There are more reasons for the subjective element to appear in the evaluation of abstract things than in the evaluation of concrete things. Therefore, when using words that express the evaluation of abstract events, the level

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of subjectivity included in this word increases, which helps this word to become a modal.

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